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Media framing of political leaders and its impact on voting behavior: A case study of Pakistan General Elections 2024

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ABSTRACT

The media is considered the fourth pillar of the Pakistani state. In countries like Pakistan, where the democratic process is a bit slow but slowly changing due to various factors, the media also plays a major role in this process. This study explores the impact of media framing of political leaders on voting behavior during Pakistan's General Election 2024. This study seeks to shed light on the dynamics of news media's effect on political outcomes by investigating whether positive and negative depictions of party leaders influence voter attitudes. Structured surveys were used to collect data from 160 (N=160) university students in Lahore, measuring their attitudes toward media portrayals and their effects on voting patterns. The findings demonstrate an important correlation between media framing and voter support, with individuals demonstrating diverse responses to positive and negative portrayals. In addition to this, time spent watching TV also has an impact on voting behavior. These findings have far-reaching consequences, highlighting the importance of political parties engaging in strategic media activities that promote positive depictions while mitigating negative frames. This study adds to the larger discussion of media influence in electoral situations, providing useful insights for policymakers, political strategists, and researchers interested in the junction of media and politics in Pakistan.

Key words: Media frames, electoral process, voting behavior, politics, political leaders

Introduction

Politics and media are inseparable in reality (Tiung, L. K., & Hasim, M. S., 2009). For the majority of people, the media is the primary source of knowledge on politics and conflicts (Vladisavljević, N., 2015). Some studies have demonstrated that politicians' framing of an issue in the media can have an impact on the opinions and attitudes of the public. The process through which people re-frame a problem or come up with a specific conceptualization of it is referred to as framing. An individual's overall opinion is directly influenced by their frame of mind (Daka, S., Li, W. A. N. G., & Chisanga., 2016). Voters often use biases to simplify and avoid their voting decisions due to their inability to understand political complexities. Media enables voters to critically examine candidate images and make future voting decisions (Tobias-Mamina, R., Maziriri, E. T., & Chiliya, N., 2021). Recent election campaigns have highlighted the role of the media on political decision-making. Media promotes interpersonal discussions among the public, influencing their decision to vote for a specific party (Sharma, A. et al., 2023). In elections, voters are influenced by party leaders' popularity. Party leaders have been shown to have a greater impact on voting over time. Leaders mean more today than they did yesterday. Leadership is becoming increasingly important (Holmberg, S., & Oscarsson, H., 2011)

Problem statement

The media uses a range of framing strategies to influence how the public perceives politicians. These strategies might highlight specific qualities, scandals, or policy stances, which can impact voters' assessments and decisions. The 2024 election in Pakistan provides a unique opportunity to investigate this dynamic because of its highly polarized political atmosphere and the significant impact of the media. The formulation of this study is to explore the major frames used by news channels and how these media frames voters' attitude, perception and eventually voting decision.

Research objectives

This research aims:

To explore different framing techniques used by the media to affect the voting behavior of the public.

To explore positive framing increases the likelihood of voting for the leader's party, while negative decreases it.

To check the relationship between the amounts of time spent viewing television and changes in voting behavior.

Research questions

To what extent do media channels influence the opinion of voters, and how much does the framing factor contribute to it?

Does the positive coverage increase the likelihood of voting, while the negative coverage decreases it?

Does time spent watching TV correlate with the change in voting decision?

Does a news channel's emphasis on specific issues (corruption, economic policies) change the perception of political leaders?

Hypothesis

H1: There is a significant relationship between media framing and voting behavior.

H2: Positive framing of a political leader is associated with greater voter support, whereas negative framing decreases the support.

H3: Time spent on TV watching is positively related with the extent to which a voter's perspective is influenced by media framing.

Literature Review

During elections, the media serves as a crucial venue for presenting political beliefs from various parties. During election campaigns, people can access political material and assess manifestos given by various parties and candidates (Yaser, N., Mahsud, N., & Chaudhry, I. A., 2011). The media's focus on leaders' appearances and ideologies leads voters to prioritize party leaders when casting their votes (Bittner, 2011, p.92). Voting decisions are fundamental to democratic societies, shaping the composition of governments and determining the policies that govern our lives. However, a variety of circumstances influence individuals' voting decisions (Kulachai, W., Lerdtomornsakul, U., & Homyamyen, P., 2023). Voters often establish opinions of party leaders based on media representations, as they rarely encounter them in person. Media coverage of party leaders is likely to influence electoral outcomes (Loes, Aaldering, et al., 2018).

Negative media coverage of electoral campaigns can harm democracy. When an election occurs during a crisis, such as a negative change in a state's affairs, the media shifts to issue or policy-based coverage to address the root cause and potential solutions (Eoin, O'Malley, et al., 2012). Research shows that the media plays a significant role in shaping voters' perceptions. Media messages are filtered by various factors, including citizens' social networks, background information, and psychological state. Party allegiance is a key determinant of voting behavior. However, there is a growing tendency for folks to avoid gatherings completely. New "populist" problems can cause followers to lose alignment. These problems often lack an established party ideology and must be avoided to gain public support. A pro-party media campaign that runs for an extended period of time will significantly impact public opinion more than one that starts two or three months prior to an election

(Nasser, N., Alotaibi., 2013)

Political leaders play a crucial role in democratic politics, as they communicate the party's message and engage people. Scholars now recognize that party leaders play a significant role in democratic elections, while previously dismissing political leadership as irrelevant to understanding voting behavior. Voters' impressions of political leaders, particularly their character attributes, have a significant impact on their voting decisions (Aaldering, L.,2018). Political understanding is a vital tool for citizens to take part in politics efficiently (Tehreem, I., & Shakeel, H., 2024).Personalized voting behavior patterns are thought to be influenced by shifting mass media structures. The combination of vocal and visual aspects inherent in broadcast communication went beyond a simple technological transition, resulting in the greatest sociological revolution of all time (Garzia, D., & De Angelis, A.,2019)

The media plays a crucial role in socialization by facilitating communication between the public and the government. Independent media can bring about enormous changes that shape the future. The media has the power to influence public opinion and rally support for a cause by emphasizing its importance and fostering consensus. It promotes unity among populations by highlighting joint challenges and aims.

It informs the public about political parties' policies, hidden agendas, and perspectives on certain issues (Umbreen, Javaid., Urwa, Elahi., 2014).The effectiveness of a frame in influencing political preference is dependent on media choice (Daka, S.,et al., 2016). Political news is frequently framed in terms of conflict .Conflicts between political players garner significant attention due to their high news value. The news media often focuses on conflicting stories, putting two sides against each other (Schuck, A. R., Vliegthart, R., & De Vreese, C. H.,2016).

Television has a tremendous impact on values, time management, agenda setting, and rules. Television has a significant impact on people's social ideals, lifestyles, and relationships with political leaders and government officials. People rely heavily on television for entertainment, information, and education (Yaser, N.et al., 2011).

Study on Political Leadership and Election Behavior demonstrates that voters' perceptions of party leaders influence their voting decisions. Positive assessments enhance the likelihood of voting for the leader's party, but bad evaluations diminish it (Loes, Aaldering., et al.,2018). Political concerns can be shown and demonstrated in a variety of ways, and how the media chooses to frame what can be used can influence how much the public and political elites think about and support particular topics. The media's power to select and choose from the discourse put forth by politicians and pressure groups gives them the opportunity to frame any political issue or upheaval (Tiung, L. K., & Hasim, M. S.,2009). The media has played an important part in politics due to its ability to quickly spread information about issues. Television news is the primary source of information for many citizens globally regarding politics and election campaigns. Television exposure affects cognitive, affective, and behavioral dimensions, as well as voting decisions (Sharma, A. et al., 2023)

Theoretical framework

In the complicated environment of political communication, how the media portrays political leaders has a significant impact on public opinion. This study uses Framing Theory as the major theoretical lens to investigate the impact of media framing on voting behavior. Framing theory, first proposed by Erving Goffman (1974) and later refined by scholars like Robert Entman (1993), holds that how the media frames or constructs a story has a substantial impact on how audiences perceive and understand that information. The framing of political leaders' attributes, actions, and policies can

result in significantly different voter views and electoral outcomes. Framing theory explains the strong link between media portrayal and voting behavior. Media frameworks influence how voters assess political leaders, so the consequences for electoral conduct can be severe. This theoretical framework will be used to critically examine how media outlets in countries like Pakistan frame political leaders during election campaigns, as well as the impact this has on voter decisions. Through this lens, the study hopes to explore the complicated relationship between media narratives and voter behavior, providing deeper insights into the mechanics of democratic processes.

Research Methodology

Research design

In this research, quantitative methodology was used to measure and to answer all the research questions about the gender gap in political knowledge among students by using software SPSS.

POPULATION

For this current research study, the population was from 4 different public and private sector universities of Lahore, namely: PU, UCP, UMT, and UOL.

Sampling technique and sample size

The questionnaire was designed to collect data. The data was collected by random convenience sampling. The sample size was 160 students.

Findings and interpretations

For this research paper, data were collected from 160 participants (N=160) belonging to different universities in Lahore with the help of convenience sampling. A wide range of respondents were asked to know about their consumption of news from television, their political interest, and views about political figures. Out of which 60.9% are male and 39.1% are female. All are from different levels of education i.e (36.9% with 16 years of education, 40.2% with 18 years of education and 20.7% possess with other different educational backgrounds, with different news consumption patterns.

Reliability of Data

For checking the reliability of the data, a reliability test is being done with the help of SPSS. And resultant value is 0.758(table: 1.1) which indicates that the collected data has good reliability.

Table:1 Case Processing Summary

		N	%
Cases	Valid	160	100.0
	Excluded	0	.0
	Total	160	100.0

Table:1.1 Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
.758	.815	20

Bivariate spearman's correlation test

To test the H1 significance of the relationship between media framing and voting behavior, A Bivariate spearman's rho correlation test is performed by using SPSS. It is used to test the relationship between two variables. Either both variables have some association with one another or not.

Table:2 Correlations

			political leaders are differently framed on TV	Media framing changed the voting behavior during elections
Spearman's rho	political leaders are differently framed on TV	Correlation Coefficient	1.000	.133
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.	.093
		N	160	160
	media significantly changed the voting behavior during elections	Correlation Coefficient	.133	1.000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.093	.
		N	160	160

The Spearman's correlation between the perception that political leaders are differently framed on TV and the belief that media significantly changed voting behavior during elections yielded a correlation coefficient of 0.133. This indicates a weak positive relationship, suggesting that individuals who believe political leaders are framed differently on TV are slightly more likely to think that media has influenced voting behavior.

Paired sample t-test

To test the H2 that positive framing increases the voter support and negative decreases it. A paired t test performed through SPSS.

Table 3: Paired Sample Statistics

	Mean	N	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	Error
Positive	12.7063	160	3.22841	.25523	

framing				
Negative framing	12.8688	160	4.78615	.37838

The paired samples statistics revealed that participants rated negative framing (M = 12.87, SD = 4.79) slightly higher than positive framing (M = 12.71, SD = 3.23). The mean difference of **-0.1625** indicates a minimal difference in the influence of framing types.

Table 4 Paired Sample Correlations

	N	Correlation	Sig.
Positive framing & Negative framing	160	.543	.000

A moderate positive correlation ($r = 0.543$, $p = 0.000$) was identified between positive and negative framing, suggesting that respondents who rated one type of framing higher also tended to rate the other type higher. This interdependence in perceptions highlights the complexity of media influence.

Table 5 Paired Samples Test

	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference		T(df)	Sig. (2-tailed)
				Lower	Upper		
Positive framing- Negative framing	-.16250	4.06842	.32164	-.79773	.47273	-.505 159	.614

The paired samples t-test yielded a t-statistic of -0.505 with a p-value of 0.614. Since the p-value exceeds the significance level of **0.05**, the study fails to reject the null hypothesis, indicating no statistically significant difference between voter support influenced by positive and negative framing. The 95% Confidence Interval for the mean difference included zero, reinforcing this conclusion.

The findings do not support the hypothesis that positive framing of a political leader is associated with greater voter support, whereas negative framing decreases support. Instead, the lack of a significant difference suggests that, within this sample, both types of framing exert a similar influence on voter attitudes.

Bivariate correlation test

To test the H3 that time spent on TV has a positive impact on the opinion of viewers again spearman’s correlation test performed by using SPSS.

The analysis is based on a sample size of **160 participants**, which provides a solid foundation for statistical analysis.

Table 6 Correlations

			time spent	news channels influence opinion
Spearman's rho	time spent	Correlation Coefficient	1.000	.077
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.	.334
		N	160	160
	news channels influence opinion	Correlation Coefficient	.077	1.000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.334	.
		N	160	160

The Spearman’s rho correlation analysis between time spent on news channels and news channels' influence on opinions resulted in a **correlation coefficient of 0.077**, indicating a **very weak positive relationship**. This suggests that individuals who spend more time watching news channels may report a slightly higher tendency to be influenced by them. However, the strength of this relationship is minimal.

Conclusion

There are many studies related to media and electoral processes in different democracies. However, in this study researchers particularly conducted a study on the Pakistani general election of 2024. Television is the main source of information in this country. But the question arises, is the public still influenced by the narrative created by news channels in 2024? By the end of this article researchers concluded that the minor influence of news media still exists. And it may still cause a change in voting perception. However, the frames set by the media may not increase or decrease the voter support for any particular political leader. Stats clearly show that positive and negative framing of different political leaders does not have an impact on young voters. They are still not greatly influenced by TV news. However, the time spent watching the news on TV may slightly change their voting behavior. On the other hand, emergence of social media during the 2024 elections may be a factor that affects the influence of traditional media like TV but it is not studied in this research.

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